

Appendix A

Dataset

Purpose	Filename
Training Dataset	Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_selected_90.csv
Real Label Dataset	Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv
Test Dataset	Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv

Zero-shot Prompting

- Inputs to LLM:
 - Test Dataset
 - Real Label Dataset
- Requirements for the model to classify according to predefined rules

- Task Overview

This task primarily consists of two sub-tasks: first, to perform multi-class classification on data from a specified CSV file and generate a new CSV file; and second, to evaluate the classification results using specific evaluation metrics and to plot relevant charts.

- Subtask 1: Data Classification and New File Generation

- Task Description data in `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` file, for each row, using `Person ID`, `Gender`, `Age`, `Occupation`, `Sleep Duration`, `Quality of Sleep`, `Physical Activity Level`, `Stress Level`, `BMI Category`, `Blood Pressure`, `Heart Rate`, `Daily Steps` as features, perform multi-class classification on each row of data. The classification results are of three types: `normal`, `Sleep Apnea`, `Insomnia`. Insert the classification result into the last column of each row, with the column name `Sleep Disorder`, and generate a new CSV file for download. The new file name is `classifiers_by_90samples.csv`
- Detailed Steps
 1. read `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` file with appropriate libraries (e.g.pandas).
 2. Feature Extraction: Extract the specified feature columns `Person ID`, `Gender`, `Age`, `Occupation`, `Sleep Duration`, `Quality of Sleep`, `Physical Activity Level`, `Stress Level`, `BMI Category`, `Blood Pressure`, `Heart Rate`, `Daily Steps`.
 3. Multi-class Classification: Based on the feature data and predefined classification rules, classify each row of data to obtain classification results (`normal`, `Sleep Apnea`, `Insomnia`).
 4. Result Insertion: Insert the classification result into the last column of each row, with the column name `Sleep Disorder`.
 5. File Saving: Save the processed data as a new CSV file `classifiers_by_90samples.csv`.

- Subtask 2: Classification Result Evaluation and Visualization

- Task Description
- Take the third uploaded file (filename `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv`) and the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file generated in the first step as input. Use `sklearn.metrics` in `accuracy_score`, `precision_score`, `f1_score`, `recall_score`, `confusion_matrix`, `roc_curve`, `auc` and other evaluation metrics to calculate the evaluation values of the classification results and draw relevant charts.
- Detailed Steps

1. Data Reading: Use `pandas` to read the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv` and `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` files separately.
2. Label Extraction: Extract the real labels from the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv` file and the predicted labels from the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file.
3. Evaluation Metric Calculation: Use the corresponding functions in `sklearn.metrics` to calculate `accuracy_score` (accuracy), `precision_score` (precision), `f1_score` (F1 score), `recall_score` (recall), `confusion_matrix` (confusion matrix), `roc_curve` (ROC curve), and `auc` (Area Under the ROC Curve).
4. Result Output: Output and display the calculated evaluation metric values.
5. Chart Drawing: Use `matplotlib` or other plotting libraries to draw confusion matrix plots and ROC curves to visually display the evaluation of classification results.

- Output Requirements

- After completing subtask 1, provide a download link for the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file.
- After completing subtask 2, output the calculated evaluation metric values and display the drawn confusion matrix plot and ROC curve plot.

90-sample Prompting

- Inputs to LLM:

- Training Dataset
- Test Dataset
- Real Label Dataset

- Requirements for the model to classify based on the data patterns in the training set

- Task Overview

This task primarily consists of two sub-tasks: first, to perform multi-class classification on data from a specified CSV file and generate a new CSV file; and second, to evaluate the classification results using specific evaluation metrics and to plot relevant charts.

- Subtask 1: Data Classification and New File Generation

- Data Source: Use data from the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` file. This file contains sample information to be classified, but does not contain the target classification column.
- Feature Selection: Classify using `Person ID`, `Gender`, `Age`, `Occupation`, `Sleep Duration`, `Quality of Sleep`, `Physical Activity Level`, `Stress Level`, `BMI Category`, `Blood Pressure`, `Heart Rate`, `Daily Steps` as features.
- Classification Reference: Refer to the data patterns in the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_selected_90.csv` file, the corresponding relationship between features and classification results, and other information. Based on the feature data, use a `softmax` classifier to perform multi-class classification on each row of data. The classification results are of three types: `normal`, `Sleep Apnea`, `Insomnia`.
- Result Processing: in `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` add one column with name `Sleep Disorder`, which is the classification result.
- File Saving: Generate a new CSV file `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` for download. This file contains the original feature data and the predicted classification results.

- Subtask 2: Classification Result Evaluation and Visualization

- Data Input: Take `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv` and the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` generated in the first step as input data. Among them, `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv` contains the real classification labels, and `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` contains the predicted classification labels.
- Evaluation Metric Calculation: Use the `accuracy_score` (accuracy), `precision_score` (precision), `f1_score` (F1 score), `recall_score` (recall), `confusion_matrix` (confusion matrix), `roc_curve` (ROC curve), and `auc` (Area Under the ROC Curve) functions in the `sklearn.metrics` library to calculate the evaluation metrics of the classification results. For multi-class problems, `precision_score`, `f1_score`, and `recall_score` can use appropriate averaging strategies (such as `weighted`).
- Result Presentation: Output the calculated values of each evaluation metric in a clear format to clearly show the classification effect.

- Visualization Display: Use appropriate plotting libraries (such as `matplotlib`) to draw confusion matrix plots and ROC curves to visually present the accuracy and performance of the classification results.
- Output Requirements
 - After completing subtask 1, provide a download link for the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file.
 - After completing subtask 2, output the values of each evaluation metric in a clear format and display the drawn confusion matrix plot and ROC curve plot.

Decomposed Prompting

- Inputs to LLM:
 - Training Dataset
 - Test Dataset
 - Real Label Dataset
- Requirements for the model to decompose the task into multiple subtasks, and gradually guide the model to design, train, and test the classifier

- Task Overview

This task primarily consists of two sub-tasks: first, to perform multi-class classification on data from a specified CSV file and generate a new CSV file; and second, to evaluate the classification results using specific evaluation metrics and to plot relevant charts.
- Subtask 1: Data Classification and New File Generation
 - 1. Data Reading and Preparation
 - * Read the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_selected_90.csv` file as the training set. This file should contain the feature columns `Person ID`, `Gender`, `Age`, `Occupation`, `Sleep Duration`, `Quality of Sleep`, `Physical Activity Level`, `Stress Level`, `BMI Category`, `Blood Pressure`, `Heart Rate`, `Daily Steps` and the corresponding classification labels (`normal`, `Sleep Apnea`, `Insomnia`).
 - * Read the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` file as the test set. This file only contains the above feature columns and does not contain classification labels.
 - 2. Feature Processing and Model Training
 - * Preprocess the data of the training set and test set as necessary, such as encoding categorical features (e.g., `Gender`, `Occupation`, `BMI Category`) and standardizing numerical features to ensure that the data is suitable for model training.
 - * Using `Person ID`, `Gender`, `Age`, `Occupation`, `Sleep Duration`, `Quality of Sleep`, `Physical Activity Level`, `Stress Level`, `BMI Category`, `Blood Pressure`, `Heart Rate`, `Daily Steps` as features and the classification labels in the training set as the target, automatically design, train, and test various classifiers until the accuracy is above 0.95, and then stop training.
 - 3. Prediction and Result Saving
 - * Input each row of `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90_without_last_column.csv` (test set) into the trained linear classifier for prediction to obtain the classification result (`normal`, `Sleep Apnea`, `Insomnia`) corresponding to each row of data.
 - * Insert the prediction result into the last column of the test set data, with the column name `Sleep Disorder`.
 - * Generate a new CSV file `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` for download. This file contains the original feature data of the test set and the predicted classification results.
- Subtask 2: Classification Result Evaluation and Visualization
 - 1. Data Reading and Label Extraction
 - * Read the `Sleep_health_and_lifestyle_dataset_remaining_90.csv` file, which contains the real classification labels of the test set data.
 - * Read the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file generated in the first step and extract the predicted classification labels from it.
 - 2. Evaluation Metric Calculation

- * Use the `accuracy_score` (accuracy), `precision_score` (precision), `f1_score` (F1 score), `recall_score` (recall), `confusion_matrix` (confusion matrix), `roc_curve` (ROC curve), and `auc` (Area Under the ROC Curve) functions in the `sklearn.metrics` library to calculate the evaluation metrics of the classification results. For multi-class problems, `precision_score`, `f1_score`, and `recall_score` can use appropriate averaging strategies (such as `weighted`).
- 3. Result Presentation and Visualization
 - * Output the calculated values of each evaluation metric in a clear format for easy viewing and analysis.
 - * Use plotting libraries such as `matplotlib` and `seaborn` to draw confusion matrix plots and ROC curves to visually display the accuracy and performance of the classification results.
- Output Requirements
 - After completing subtask 1, provide a download link for the `classifiers_by_90samples.csv` file.
 - After completing subtask 2, output the values of each evaluation metric in a clear format and display the drawn confusion matrix plot and ROC curve plot.